

Scope & Topics

Natural Language Processing is a programmed approach to analyze text that is based on both a set of theories and a set of technologies. This forum aims to bring together researchers who have designed and build software that will analyze, understand, and generate languages that humans use naturally to address computers.

Topics of interest include but are not limited to, the following

- Phonology, Morphology
- Chunking/Shallow Parsing
- Parsing/Grammatical Formalisms
- Semantic Processing
- Lexical Semantics
- Ontology
- Linguistic Resources
- Statistical and Knowledge based methods
- POS tagging
- Discourse
- Paraphrasing/Entailment/Generation
- Machine Translation
- Information Retrieval
- Text Mining
- Information Extraction
- Question Answering
- Dialog Systems
- Spoken Language Processing
- Speech Recognition and Synthesis

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: ijnlcjournal@yahoo.com or ijnlc@airconline.com. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : June 04, 2022**
- Notification : July 04, 2022
- Final Manuscript Due : July 12s, 2022
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact us:

Here's where you can reach us : ijnlc@airconline.com

Submission URL: <http://coneco2009.com/submissions/imagination/home.html>